

YOU'RE HIRED: DETERMINING THE CRITERIA IN RECRUITMENT AND HIRING SELECTION OF REPUBLIC GAS CORPORATION LOCATED IN CITY OF CALACA, BATANGAS

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Abstract

Finding the right employees is crucial for any company's success and effective hiring criteria is a key factor in achieve it. This study investigates the criteria in recruitment and hiring selection of Republic Gas Corporation (REGASCO) in City of Calaca, Batangas. A qualitative descriptive research design and purposive sampling was used and this study conducted semi-structured interviews with selected officers responsible for recruitment at REGASCO. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis. The findings shows that REGASCO prioritizes educational qualifications, relevant work experience, skill set, and overall job fit in their hiring policies. However, issues such as late document submissions, applicant-job role mismatches, and ineffective advertising to attract qualified personnel were identified. The study concludes that while REGASCO has managerial policies aimed at securing competent employees, recruitment barriers can be addressed through a direct employee selection program. This study proposes an action plan to improve recruitment practices, focusing on diversifying marketing channels, enhancing the pre-qualifying stage, and improving company image to attract suitable candidates. The study's implications extend beyond REGASCO, Calaca, Batangas, offering valuable insights for other companies seeking to optimize their hiring strategies.

Keywords: *Recruitment, Hiring Selection Criteria, Thematic Analysis, Qualitative, Republic Gas Corporation (REGASCO), Employee Selection.*

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INTRODUCTION

Recruitment was the process of inviting applicants for jobs through a procedure that began with sourcing candidates and conducting interviews. This process was the main function of the HR department; it was the first step in making an organization competitive (Hamza et al., 2021). Recruitment was the initial portion of choosing employees, followed by the selection process, which involved evaluating and interviewing candidates to find the right person for the right position. According to Kapur (2018), employers chose a suitable candidate through a process called selection. In addition, selection was the process of choosing an appropriate candidate among the job applicants. Moreover, according to Tanu et al. (2023), it was the recruitment and selection process that determined the long-term success of the organization. They also emphasized the importance of using recruitment and selection to choose the right person to do the right job at the right time.

Criteria, on the other hand, were essential conditions used to select and evaluate candidates during the hiring process. These specifically referred to the standards or requirements used in determining the level of quality and effectiveness needed in a particular activity (Rado, 2024). Additionally, criteria served as guidelines or regulations that aided in making decisions or judgments, specifically in the hiring process, as they ensured that the selected applicants possessed qualifications aligned with the requirements of the job. According to Meyer (2024), establishing the criteria was important during the recruitment and hiring selection process, which started from the initial person specification until making the job offer. Selecting the most appropriate and deserving employee for a position was critical to the success of an organization, and the right criteria made it easier to identify highly qualified employees and reduce biases as well as discrimination in the organization, thereby increasing the effectiveness of the hiring process (Nallalingham, 2023). Furthermore, the significance of enhancing recruitment and hiring selection processes using relevant criteria supported an organization's personnel selection, staffing models, and employee development objectives (Mayhew, 2024).

The use of criteria in recruitment and selection was particularly important in industries facing talent shortages. For example, according to Nguyen (2022), labor shortages in oil and gas companies were one of the most serious risks in the industry. Skill shortages in the oil and gas industry affected productivity, and there were widening gaps in every sector of the industry (Hudik, 2019). In the oil and gas sector, fuel, gasoline, and petroleum represented the largest volume of products (Mauspratt, 2019). Liquid petroleum gas was essential for cooking and heating in households, so ensuring the safe delivery and production of LPG required a skilled workforce. Republic Gas Corporation (REGASCO) was a major LPG provider in the Philippines, with one of its refilling plants located in the City of Calaca, Batangas. This area had a growing population with 81 employees, making it significant to know what kind of criteria the company looked for in its hiring process. According to Hammeed et al. (2016), LPG skid plants played an important role in meeting residents' needs and refilling gas cylinders in local areas. Proper care and attention during the refilling process were necessary, as this could lead to accidents and harm individuals. A leakage from an LPG tank caused an explosion in a fast-food chain (Garcia, 2022). The study highlighted the importance of carefully choosing employees and their criteria in hiring to ensure the safety of everyone involved in the refilling process, even the consumers. This incident underscored the need for a strict evaluation of the qualifications of employees to prevent similar accidents.

Most studies discussed the recruitment and hiring practices of companies but often failed to delve into the specific criteria they used to evaluate candidates. This was particularly relevant for companies like REGASCO, which prioritized the safety of numerous individuals. Therefore, the aims of this study were to identify and analyze the criteria

that Republic Gas Corporation employed in its recruitment and hiring selection process and to assess how these criteria ensured the quality and suitability of hired employees. Furthermore, this study sought to understand the challenges the company encountered in its hiring process and to develop an action plan that could help not just the company but the applicants too.

The researchers presumed that by determining the criteria, the recruitment and hiring selection processes could be improved and enhanced. These improvements were vital to aligning with the expectations of human resource personnel. This study provided valuable insights into what criteria a gas corporation looked for.

Objectives

The objective of this study is to investigate the criteria utilized by Republic Gas Corporation in the recruitment and hiring selection processes in the City of Calaca, Batangas. The study aims to address the following specific questions:

1. What criteria does Republic Gas Corporation employ in its recruitment and hiring selection processes?
2. How effective are these criteria in ensuring the quality and suitability of hired employees?
3. What challenges does Republic Gas Corporation encounter during the recruitment and selection process?
4. Based on the findings, what action plan should be recommended to improve the recruitment and hiring practices at Republic Gas Corporation?

METHODS

The researchers employed a descriptive design and qualitative method to collect data to determine the recruitment and selection criteria utilized by Republic Gas Corporation. This method addressed the need for a deep understanding of the organization's practices, while the descriptive design provided a structured overview of the recruitment and selection processes, serving as the foundation for qualitative inquiries. In-depth interviews with the hiring personnel revealed the underlying rationale, challenges, and criteria that influenced the organization's hiring decisions. By combining these approaches, the study provided comprehensive and informative data about the hiring practices of Republic Gas Corporation.

The insights derived from this study enabled the researchers to gain a deeper understanding of the actual problems and issues faced by Republic Gas Corporation during hiring and to identify the company's recruitment and selection criteria. By avoiding assumptions that did not often reflect actual social realities, the qualitative method emphasized the direct experiences and phenomena described by the study's participants. Through a thorough assessment of both descriptive and qualitative data, the researchers detailed the specific factors valued by the organization in its hiring process. The descriptive design allowed the researchers to provide a detailed account of the current recruitment and hiring selection processes at Republic Gas Corporation, identifying and describing the specific criteria prioritized during these processes.

Population and Sampling

The study employed purposive sampling, which allowed the researchers to select participants possessing specific characteristics or having experienced particular events relevant to the study's focus. In this case, the researchers examined the criteria for recruitment and hiring selection within Republic Gas Corporation in the City of Calaca, Batangas. Using purposive sampling emphasized efficiency in data selection for qualitative research. The researchers selected participants from Republic Gas Corporation who provided valuable perspectives and firsthand experiences regarding the criteria utilized in recruitment and hiring selection. This sampling method aligned with the study's goal of capturing detailed data from individuals who could provide rich insights into the organization's hiring practices.

Research Instrument

To achieve the study's objectives, the researchers utilized a single data collection instrument: a semi-structured interview with systematically formulated questions, allowing for flexibility and detailed responses. Semi-structured interviews enabled open-ended questions to explore participants' experiences and perspectives in depth. The interview protocol included standardized open-ended questions and a structured introduction to explain the study's purpose. This method allowed the interviewer to address specific concerns with prepared questions while also probing deeper based on participants' responses. This approach facilitated the collection of participants' personal narratives, which formed the foundation of qualitative research.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers conducted interviews either via video calls or in person, based on mutual agreement with the participants. They ensured that participants had sufficient time to express themselves without interfering with their normal work schedules. These interviews, lasting 30 to 45 minutes, provided participants the opportunity to share detailed information on various recruitment-related topics. With participants' consent, the researchers securely stored all collected data on a password-protected electronic device to safeguard both the documents and participants' information. The interviews were then transcribed and carefully assessed.

The transcriptions were analyzed to uncover the hiring criteria used by Republic Gas Corporation. The researchers compiled responses, conducted critical analyses, and identified consistent themes and trends related to recruitment techniques and employee recruitment strategies. An external examiner reviewed the findings to validate the study's authenticity and reliability.

Data Analysis

The study employed a sequential analysis approach using rigorous methods. Initially, the researchers conducted interviews and repeatedly reviewed the text to derive meaningful interpretations. Thematic coding was applied to systematically organize the data, simplifying the analysis process. Through this approach, the researchers categorized information and identified patterns, defining themes and sub-themes that addressed the study's objectives. The researchers grouped coded data into patterns and significant observations, aligning themes and sub-themes with the research questions. Member checking was employed to validate the findings, involving participants in verifying results to enhance reliability and address potential discrepancies, such as double-counting data from various sources.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers adhered to ethical standards by providing participants with clear information about the study's purpose before their involvement. Informed consent ensured that participants made voluntary decisions to participate. The researchers maintained the privacy and confidentiality of participants' information in compliance with RA 10173, the Data Privacy Act, ensuring that personal identifiers were kept confidential to prevent any potential harm.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Recruitment and Hiring Criteria at Republic Gas Corporation

Republic Gas Corporation (Regasco) has a structured recruitment and hiring process that prioritizes key factors such as educational attainment, relevant work experience, essential skills, and job fit. Based on interviews with employees, it is evident that Regasco's selection process aims to identify candidates who not only meet the technical demands of their respective roles but also align with the company's operational needs. The basic criteria are the following:

1. Educational Attainment (Participant 1)
2. Work Experience (Participant 2, Participant 3, Participant 5)
3. Skills and Competencies (Participant 2, Participant 4, Participant 5)
4. Job Fit and Knowledge (Participant 3)

1. Educational Attainment

A core criterion in Regasco's recruitment process is educational attainment. The company applies different standards for varying levels of responsibility to ensure candidates possess the academic background necessary for specific roles. Higher-level positions, such as those in management or administration, require college graduates who are equipped with critical thinking skills, advanced knowledge, and specialized training. For entry-level roles, such as stockman and delivery personnel, the minimum requirement is a Senior High School diploma, emphasizing the practical skills and efficiency needed for operational tasks. This approach ensures that the educational qualifications of candidates align with the demands of their roles.

Participant 1 emphasized, "The qualifications must be College Graduate for the higher positions and at least Senior High School Graduate for the lower positions like the stockman and delivery man." This statement underscores the organization's commitment to setting academic benchmarks tailored to the complexity of the job. Higher-level positions benefit from candidates with advanced academic training, while foundational education suffices for roles focused on execution and logistics. Similarly, (Lievens and Chapman, 2017) emphasize that educational background is a key criterion in recruitment as it ensures candidates are prepared to meet the role's demands.

Educational attainment is seen as a marker of a candidate's discipline, ability to adapt, and potential for professional growth. College graduates often bring analytical skills and a deeper understanding of the workplace, making them suitable for strategic and decision-making roles. In contrast, Senior High School graduates are well-suited

for positions requiring reliability and hands-on application, ensuring that each role is filled by individuals who meet the basic educational requirements.

This emphasis on educational qualifications reflects the company's objective of fostering a competent and diverse workforce. College graduates in leadership roles are equipped to guide teams effectively, using their academic background to address complex challenges. For operational roles, the inclusion of Senior High School graduates ensures that opportunities remain accessible to individuals with different educational levels, as long as they demonstrate the ability to meet the job's specific requirements.

Educational qualifications also streamline the recruitment process, serving as an initial filter to identify candidates who are best suited for specific roles. Establishing clear academic standards allows the organization to focus on evaluating other critical criteria such as skills, experience, and work ethic, knowing that applicants already meet the baseline requirements. This structured approach demonstrates Regasco's commitment to a fair and efficient hiring process, ensuring candidates are assessed holistically.

The focus on educational attainment supports the broader organizational goal of building a capable and professional workforce. Employees with the appropriate educational background for their positions are better equipped to meet job expectations and contribute to the company's success. This alignment of qualifications with job demands helps maintain a workplace culture that values competence, adaptability, and growth. As Regasco continues to evolve, the emphasis on educational attainment will remain integral to its recruitment and hiring practices.

2. Work Experience

Work experience is a critical factor in Regasco's recruitment and hiring process, especially for roles related to the gas industry. The company values candidates with a proven track record in positions that require relevant industry-specific skills. Prior experience serves as evidence of a candidate's preparedness for the responsibilities of the role and their ability to quickly adapt to the operational demands of the organization.

Participant 2 highlighted this, stating, *"They must be capable enough in multitasking and have the long-time span of experience that will help them in the gas industry."* This statement underscores the importance of experience in enabling candidates to handle the fast-paced and often complex nature of their responsibilities. Multitasking, a key requirement in the gas industry, is more effectively mastered through years of professional experience, equipping candidates with the ability to address multiple challenges simultaneously. Particularly, (Mcconnell, 2024) emphasizes that determining a candidate's suitability for a role is critical and experience is one of its bases.

The role of work experience was further emphasized by **Participant 3**, who noted, *"Yes po, we need to select the qualified applicant or candidate based on the background they provide to us, parang mas maraming experience or bala sa position mas Malaki ang chance na makuha. Kailangan marami kang maiioffer samin to hire you."* This highlights how experience directly influences hiring decisions. Applicants with significant experience in similar roles are seen as better equipped to meet job expectations and contribute meaningfully to the company's operations without requiring extensive training. Similarly, according to (Herrity, 2024) the experience that an applicant has can be beneficial for them as it can help in gaining skills and standing among all the applicants.

Work experience is often viewed as a practical indicator of a candidate's ability to navigate real-world challenges in their role. It reflects their familiarity with industry-specific practices, their problem-solving capabilities,

and their capacity to perform consistently under pressure. Candidates with experience bring valuable insights that enhance operational efficiency and help the company achieve its objectives more effectively.

Although work experience is a priority, the company acknowledges that it is not the sole determinant in hiring decisions. **Participant 4** mentioned, *"I don't think so, kasi sometimes may nahahire on the spot kahit kulang sa experience but good ang educational background, depende sa position na hinahanap."* This statement reflects Regasco's flexibility in evaluating candidates holistically. In some instances, strong educational qualifications or other attributes may offset a lack of extensive experience, particularly for roles that prioritize theoretical knowledge or specialized training. Further, according to (Ziwewe, 2024) employers think that being motivated, and eager to develop and to learn new things is a quality of an individual who has work experience and it improves their employability.

The emphasis on work experience reflects the company's strategic approach to building a workforce capable of addressing the demands of the gas industry. Candidates with relevant professional backgrounds are more likely to excel in their roles, contribute to the organization's success, and maintain high standards of productivity. At the same time, the organization's willingness to consider exceptional candidates with less experience demonstrates an inclusive and dynamic recruitment process tailored to meet the needs of specific positions. This balance ensures that Regasco can attract and retain a diverse pool of talent suited to various roles within the company.

3. Skills and Competencies

Regasco emphasizes the importance of skills and competencies in its recruitment and hiring process. Beyond education and experience, specific skills such as communication, multitasking, and a strong work ethic are critical for success in the gas industry. The company prioritizes hiring individuals who possess the technical and interpersonal skills necessary to excel in a fast-paced and dynamic environment. These competencies enable employees to manage tasks efficiently, maintain high performance, and contribute effectively to organizational goals.

Participant 4 highlighted the value of communication, stating, *"Maybe the experience tsaka yung good communicating skills because it is very important in a hiring process."* as according to (Schwencke, 2024) skilled interviewees can effectively communicate their positive qualities during interviews even if the interview may not be a perfect measure of all qualities. Communication skills are vital for many roles at Regasco, as employees often interact with customers, suppliers, and colleagues. Clear and effective communication ensures that operations run smoothly, that issues are promptly addressed, and that team collaboration is fostered. In an industry where safety, efficiency, and customer satisfaction are essential, the ability to communicate effectively plays a central role in achieving these objectives.

Multitasking is another key competency that Regasco considers essential for its employees. **Participant 2** emphasized this, stating, *"They must be capable enough in multitasking."* Multitasking is particularly crucial in the gas industry, where roles frequently involve handling overlapping responsibilities. The ability to manage multiple tasks without compromising quality allows employees to adapt to shifting priorities and maintain productivity under pressure. This skill ensures that operations remain efficient and responsive to the demands of the industry, even during challenging situations. In addition, (Kaushik, 2024) notes that recruitment companies list particular skills that they need and desire in job postings.

Dedication and a strong work ethic are equally important in Regasco's hiring process. **Participant 5** remarked, *"Yes, the skills and being hardworking are essential as qualifications in applying at Regasco."* According to

(Ramos, 2024) aside from prioritizing traditional qualifications, skills-based hiring is known to evaluate job applicants based on their demonstrated competencies and how is this relevant to the role they are applying for. A strong work ethic reflects a candidate's commitment to their responsibilities and their ability to persevere in demanding circumstances. Hardworking employees contribute to a culture of reliability and accountability, enhancing the overall performance and cohesion of the workforce. This quality is particularly valued in roles that require sustained effort and adaptability to meet organizational objectives.

The emphasis on skills and competencies ensures that Regasco recruits a workforce equipped to address the challenges of the gas industry. Employees with strong communication abilities, multitasking proficiency, and a robust work ethic contribute to operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. These attributes not only enhance individual performance but also strengthen the collective capability of the organization to meet its goals. Focusing on these qualities during recruitment enables Regasco to maintain high standards of service and achieve sustained success in a competitive industry.

4. Job Fit and Knowledge

Regasco places significant emphasis on job fit and industry-specific knowledge when assessing candidates. Meeting the basic educational and experience requirements is only part of what the company seeks; candidates must also align with the specific demands of the roles they are applying for. This alignment ensures that employees can integrate seamlessly into their teams and start contributing effectively from day one. Prioritizing job fit and knowledge helps Regasco maintain a competent and efficient workforce, which is essential in the competitive gas industry.

Participant 3 emphasized this aspect, stating, "*The Regasco is looking for a qualified applicant that has good background, experience, and knowledge about the position and environment they will be belonging with.*" This statement underscores the importance of hiring candidates who not only meet the qualifications but also possess a deep understanding of their prospective roles.

This includes familiarity with the responsibilities, challenges, and industry-specific practices. Knowledge of the position ensures that employees can adapt quickly, reducing the learning curve and contributing to operational success from the outset. (Zhang et al. 2023) claim that occupational ideals, values, and desired reinforcement in their professions can lead to positive assessments and emotional experiences of the work environment, thereby enabling ongoing engagement in current employment.

Regasco's focus on job fit reflects its commitment to long-term success and employee retention. When candidates align well with the role and the company culture, they are more likely to remain motivated, perform efficiently, and stay with the organization over the long term. Hiring individuals with relevant industry knowledge minimizes disruptions in operations, as these candidates often require less training and can handle tasks with greater confidence and precision.

Ensuring job fit also supports team dynamics and collaboration. Employees with an understanding of their roles and the industry are better equipped to work cohesively with others. Their familiarity with industry standards allows them to communicate effectively, contribute innovative ideas, and address challenges proactively. This holistic approach to hiring strengthens the overall efficiency and effectiveness of Regasco's workforce.

The emphasis on job fit and knowledge in Regasco's recruitment strategy not only ensures the selection of competent employees but also fosters a productive and harmonious workplace. Choosing candidates who bring the right mix of qualifications, experience, and understanding sustains the company's reputation for excellence and operational reliability in the gas sector. This approach reflects a forward-thinking recruitment philosophy that aligns with the company's long-term objectives. Furthermore, according to (Trysantika et. al., 2023) in a company, the suitability between the ability of workers and the demands of their work is an important thing to consider where employees are one of the company's assets. Republic Gas Corporation's recruitment and hiring process reflects a thorough and strategic approach to selecting candidates who meet both the technical and cultural needs of the company. Educational attainment, relevant work experience, essential skills, and job fit are the core pillars of their hiring criteria. Evaluating candidates across these dimensions, Regasco ensures that it hires individuals who are not only capable but also well-suited to contribute positively to the company's long-term success.

The Effectiveness of Hiring Criteria in Ensuring Quality and Suitability of Employees

When companies hire employees based on appropriate criteria, it brings significant benefits to both the employees and the organization. Using well-defined criteria ensures that candidates are a good fit for the role, leading to improved performance, retention, efficiency, and organizational success. Below are the key themes that explain the impact of hiring based on suitable criteria, supported by the participants' statements.

1. Better Employee Job Fit and Performance (Participant 1, Participant 4)
2. Improved Employee Retention and Satisfaction (Participant 3, Participant 5)
3. Streamlined Hiring Process and Cost Savings (Participant 3)
4. Enhanced Organizational Growth and Success (Participant 1, Participant 2)

1. Better Employee Job Fit and Performance

Hiring employees based on the appropriate criteria ensures that the candidates selected are well-suited for the job, leading to better job performance. **Participant 1** states, "The qualification was posted and they will apply for the desired position they are suited for," highlighting that when qualifications are clearly defined and communicated, candidates who apply are more likely to have the necessary skills for the position. This clarity helps to match the right candidates to the right roles, ensuring a better alignment between the individual's capabilities and job requirements. According to (Merrell, 2024) better Employee-job fit drives employee satisfaction, enhances performance, and ultimately fuels organizational growth.

Participant 4 supports this idea by emphasizing, "It is very effective that ensures yung mga nahire ay qualified," which translates to saying that hiring based on clear qualifications ensures that the people hired are qualified. When employees are hired with qualifications that match the job demands, they are more likely to perform at their best, as they are equipped with the right knowledge and skills for the job. Ensuring a good job fit is essential for hiring the right people who will stay with your organization and contribute positively to your team. (Sefcik, 2024)

This direct alignment between job requirements and employee capabilities results in higher productivity. When employees feel confident in their roles, as they know they have the required skills, they perform their tasks with greater

efficiency. The process not only boosts individual performance but also contributes to overall organizational success, as everyone is in a role they are well-equipped to handle.

1. Improved Employee Retention and Satisfaction

Hiring employees who are a good fit for the role leads to increased job satisfaction and improved employee retention. **Participant 3** notes, "If the person na nahire is okay ang performance and they know how it takes to be a good employee as well." This statement suggests that when employees are hired based on their suitability for the role and perform well, it indicates their satisfaction with the job and their ability to meet expectations. This satisfaction with their role makes employees more likely to stay with the company. As according to (Cunningham, 2024) high retention rates indicate a stable workforce, whereas high turnover rates may point to underlying problems in the company culture or management practices.

Employees who are aligned with their roles tend to feel more fulfilled, which is a key factor in their decision to stay long-term. When employees feel competent and appreciated, they are more likely to develop a sense of loyalty toward the company, reducing turnover rates. As **Participant 5** points out, "I can't give example, gawa ng hindi ko masabing effective hanggat diko nakikita performance nila in their duties " Employees who perform well show that they understand what it takes to be a good employee, which correlates with a stronger sense of purpose and job satisfaction.

Ensure that the right people are hired for the right roles, companies create an environment where employees are motivated and content in their positions. This leads to a more stable workforce, which is beneficial for long-term organizational growth. A satisfied employee is more likely to remain engaged, contributing to the success of the company. Several works of literature seem to confirm that effective retention is about more than what an organization does once an employee has been recruited. How organizations recruit and how they make available the necessary information to newcomers help motivate employees to stay on a long-term basis. (Sawaneh and Kamara, 2019)

2. Streamlined Hiring Process and Cost Savings

When hiring criteria are appropriate, the hiring process becomes more streamlined, helping the company save both time and resources. **Participant 3** explains, "It allows you to focus your attention on evaluating the most qualified individuals," which highlights how using specific and relevant criteria makes it easier to filter out unqualified candidates early in the process. By focusing on the most qualified applicants, the company can expedite the hiring process and reduce the time spent on candidates who are not a good fit for the role. As supported by (Oleg, 2024) when it comes to attracting the best candidates, decreasing the time-to-fill and optimizing the entire workflow are important for the companies and the recruiters.

This more efficient approach results in cost savings for the company. When the hiring process is well-defined and candidates are quickly assessed based on clear qualifications, there are fewer costs associated with lengthy recruitment procedures. Participant 3's statement about focusing on qualified individuals shows how reducing the pool of applicants to the most suitable candidates can cut down on unnecessary evaluations, thereby lowering recruitment costs.

An efficient hiring process also frees up resources for other critical areas within the company, allowing the organization to invest in training and development rather than spending excessive resources on recruiting unsuitable candidates. The streamlined process benefits both the company and the employees by ensuring that only the most suitable candidates are brought on board without delays or unnecessary costs.

Enhanced Organizational Growth and Success

Hiring based on appropriate criteria contributes to the overall growth and success of the organization by ensuring that employees who are well-suited for their roles can contribute meaningfully to the company's objectives. As **Participant 1** states, "When you hire a person for a certain position he or she knows the duties and responsibilities in one discussion," emphasizing that when employees clearly understand their roles from the beginning, they can start contributing effectively right away. This alignment ensures that employees are ready to take on their responsibilities and make an immediate impact on the organization's performance. Also, according to (Levin, 2021) Many organizations struggle to achieve success and remain short-lived because of their inability to adapt to change.

Employee effectiveness, which stems from hiring the right individuals, directly correlates with the company's success. When employees are capable of fulfilling their roles, they help the company achieve its goals. **Participant 2** further asserts, "It is effective." This statement suggests that when the right qualifications are emphasized, candidates who are a good fit for the organization's needs apply, leading to a workforce that is highly capable and productive. According to (Rao, 2024) organizational success involves reaching long-term objectives, sustaining high performance, and promoting ongoing growth. This requires a comprehensive strategy that includes a clear vision and mission, effective leadership, active employee participation, a focus on customers, and a commitment to innovation.

Ultimately, an organization that hires based on appropriate criteria is positioned for long-term success. The employees hired contribute directly to the company's growth by using their skills and talents to meet the organization's goals. A well-qualified and competent workforce is a crucial factor in maintaining a competitive edge, which is essential for sustaining growth and ensuring that the company remains successful in the marketplace.

In summary, when companies hire employees based on clear and appropriate criteria, the positive impacts are clear: better job performance, higher employee retention, more efficient hiring processes, and stronger organizational growth. The statements from the participants highlight how effective hiring practices can lead to a more capable, satisfied, and productive workforce, which ultimately drives the success of the organization.

Challenges Faced by Republic Gas Corporation in the Recruitment and Selection Process

The recruitment and selection process at Republic Gas Corporation is an essential function that aims to hire the best candidates to ensure smooth operations. However, the process is not without its challenges, which can significantly affect the organization's ability to hire qualified individuals in a timely manner.

The participants in this study highlighted several key issues in the recruitment process, such as delays in document submission, difficulty in finding qualified or competent applicants, mismatches between applicants and job roles, challenges with fieldwork, and overall delays in the hiring process. This analysis explores these challenges by providing a detailed narrative explanation, using direct quotes from the participants to illustrate each theme.

1. Delays in Document Submission (Participant 1, Participant 5, Participant 2)
2. Lack of Qualified or Competent Applicants (Participant 1, Participant 5)
3. Mismatch of Applicants to Job Roles (Participant 4, Participant 3)
4. Fieldwork and Job Environment Challenges (Participant 3)
5. Delays in the Hiring Process (Participant 2, Participant 3)

1. Delays in Document Submission

A common challenge that surfaced across several participants is the delay in the submission of essential documents. These delays are typically caused by the time it takes to obtain documents like Certificates of Employment (COE) or other verification papers from previous employers. **Participant 1** highlighted this challenge by stating, "The submission of requirements," which reveals that delays in completing paperwork can create a bottleneck in the recruitment process. Document submission is a critical part of recruitment, and when applicants are unable to submit these requirements on time, it causes setbacks for the recruitment team, as they cannot proceed with the necessary evaluations or decisions. As supported by (Rindé, 2024) Applicants who start their job applications often do not finish their requirements due to complex and lengthy application processes

Participant 5 expanded on this by mentioning, "The documents that take time to release," which illustrates the external factor that can delay the submission of important paperwork. These delays may be beyond the control of both the applicants and the company, as they often depend on third parties, such as previous employers or government agencies. The impact of these delays is far-reaching, as it push back the entire recruitment timeline, causing the company to either wait longer for documents or deal with the uncertainty of applicants who cannot provide the necessary paperwork.

In addition, **Participant 2** brought up the importance of meeting deadlines by saying, "The meeting of deadlines like submission of requirements on the set date." This statement underscores the importance of adhering to timelines in the recruitment process. Delays in submitting documents not only prolong the recruitment process but also impact the company's ability to move forward with other hiring activities. When documents are not submitted on time, the company may have to delay interviews, background checks, or the decision-making process, affecting the overall efficiency of the hiring procedure. According to Try (2018), delays in the hiring process can damage the reputation of the company and also the unfilled roles have a direct impact on the productivity and revenue of the business.

2. Lack of Qualified or Competent Applicants

The second major challenge identified in the recruitment process is the lack of qualified or competent applicants. According to **Participant 1**, "Maybe if the applicant is not competent," reflects the concern that not all applicants possess the skills or qualifications required for the job. This lack of competency can make it difficult for the recruitment team to identify candidates who can meet the company's needs. When applicants do not have the necessary qualifications or experience, they cannot fulfill the demands of the position, which results in a mismatch that prolongs the recruitment cycle and hinders the company's ability to fill vacancies with the right candidates. According

to (Zivkovic, 2024), it is impossible to find a candidate who has the right mix of necessary hard and soft skills, as well as candidates that would align with the company's mission, vision, values, and culture.

Participant 5 echoed this concern by stating, "Competency, whether they are ready for the position," which emphasizes that being qualified on paper does not necessarily mean an applicant is ready for the role. Many candidates may have the educational background or certifications, but they may not have the practical experience or the skills needed to perform the tasks required in the job. This lack of readiness can make the hiring process more challenging, as the company must find candidates who are both qualified and able to adapt quickly to the work environment.

Moreover, **Participant 5** also pointed out, "Uncompetent applicants trying to force their way into positions." This statement highlights another challenge faced by Republic Gas Corporation: applicants who apply for positions they are not qualified for. These individuals may lack the skills or experience necessary for the role, but they still attempt to secure the position, creating additional challenges for the recruitment team. The presence of unqualified applicants in the recruitment pool not only slows down the process but also forces the company to spend more time screening and rejecting candidates who are not suitable for the job. Also (Teeuwen, 2022) according to Working for the Company when implementing a competency-based approach in hiring the overestimation of their interviewing capabilities leads to biases

3. Mismatch of Applicants to Job Roles

Another challenge is the mismatch between applicants and the job roles they are applying for. This mismatch can occur for several reasons, such as applicants applying for positions that do not align with their qualifications, personal preferences, or career aspirations. **Participant 4** raised this issue by saying, "Mismatch of positions to their gender identity," which suggests that some applicants may find it difficult to apply for positions that do not align with their identity. As supported by (Eaton, 2024) it is still common to have jobs focused on a specific gender in recruitment and it affects the talent pool of an organization, workplace diversity, and the company. For example, certain roles may require physical labor or a specific set of conditions that may not be appealing to all applicants, particularly when gender identity or other personal factors come into play. This mismatch can result in a workforce that is less satisfied with their roles, which could affect performance and retention.

Participant 3 also pointed out the issue of fieldwork, stating, "Finding employees willing to work in the field, especially female applicants." This highlights a common issue in industries that require fieldwork: the challenge of recruiting applicants who are willing to work in challenging conditions. Field-based roles often involve long hours, exposure to harsh environments, and physical demands that may deter applicants from applying. Participant 3's comment suggests that certain gender demographics, particularly women, may be less inclined to accept these roles, thereby narrowing the pool of potential candidates. This, in turn, increases the difficulty of filling these positions and adds to the recruitment challenges faced by Republic Gas Corporation.

The mismatch in job roles also creates an additional layer of difficulty for the recruitment team. As **Participant 5** mentioned, "Uncompetent applicants trying to force their way into positions," this reflects the fact that some candidates may not understand the full scope of the roles they are applying for, leading to misunderstandings and mismatches. It can be difficult for the recruitment team to identify candidates who truly align with the job requirements, which extends the time and effort needed to hire the right person for the job. This was supported by (Varga, 2024)

the success of a company hinges on its people, and hiring a candidate who turns out to be a mismatch can have far-reaching consequences.

4. Fieldwork and Job Environment Challenges

Fieldwork and job environment challenges are also significant barriers in the recruitment process. Many positions within Republic Gas Corporation require employees to work in outdoor or field environments, which may not be appealing to all candidates. **Participant 3** mentioned, “The fieldwork that affects their eagerness,” which illustrates that applicants may hesitate to apply for jobs that involve fieldwork, particularly when they must work in uncomfortable conditions or remote areas. This concern is particularly evident when the work requires physical labor or exposure to extreme weather conditions, which may not appeal to all individuals. Also according to (Hasan et al, 2024) Fieldwork requires loads of physicality. Their work may lead to many stresses and longer working hours as well. Slightly above two-thirds of the fieldwork involves lifting heavy items and handling sharp tools.

This issue is compounded when the recruitment team struggles to attract candidates who are willing to accept such positions. Participant 3’s statement, “Finding employees willing to work in the field, especially female applicants,” highlights that certain demographics may be less inclined to work in these environments. Fieldwork often requires a specific type of resilience, and applicants who are not prepared for the physical and mental demands may be deterred from applying. This limits the pool of potential candidates, making it harder for Republic Gas Corporation to find suitable employees for these roles.

Furthermore, the reluctance to accept field-based roles not only affects the recruitment process but also impacts the company’s ability to meet operational goals. The shortage of fieldworkers can lead to delays in service delivery, decreased productivity, and increased pressure on the existing workforce. As the company continues to face difficulties in attracting candidates for these positions, it must find ways to mitigate these challenges and make fieldwork more appealing to potential hires.

5. Delays in the Hiring Process

The culmination of the previous challenges—delays in document submission, difficulty in finding competent applicants, mismatches between applicants and job roles, and reluctance to accept field-based work—leads to delays in the overall hiring process. These delays can have serious consequences for the organization, affecting productivity and the ability to meet operational targets. **Participant 2** noted, “It may cause a delay in the hiring process,” reflecting the overall frustration caused by slow recruitment procedures. This was supported by (Berzman, 2024) the fact, that the hiring process can be prolonged because as some companies are issuing or reviewing applications, they are also doing their main business. Sometimes a company may postpone the filling of the job vacancy due to some internal factors like management or budget issues, which increases the time frame of hiring. These delays often result in a prolonged waiting period before a candidate is hired, which can put additional pressure on the existing workforce and slow down the company's growth and performance.

Participant 3 echoed this concern, stating, “Delay of hiring as well as the activity that seeks those positions.” This emphasizes how delays in the recruitment process can also impact the broader activities designed to fill these roles. When hiring is delayed, the entire process—from candidate search to onboarding—takes longer, which can cause

further delays in meeting staffing needs. As positions remain vacant for longer periods, the company may face challenges in maintaining operational efficiency and meeting deadlines. According to (Tucker, 2023) A lengthy hiring cycle can significantly raise recruitment costs. These expenses may encompass advertising, recruiter fees, employee referral bonuses, interview-related costs (like travel), background checks, and onboarding expenses such as training materials or equipment for new hires. As the hiring process drags on, these costs can accumulate rapidly, putting pressure on your company's budget.

Participant 4 added, "Production suffers if fewer people are hired," highlighting the operational risks associated with prolonged recruitment timelines. When positions remain unfilled for extended periods, the company experiences reduced workforce capacity, leading to slower production, fewer resources for ongoing projects, and potentially lost revenue. These delays in the hiring process create a ripple effect throughout the organization, undermining both short-term and long-term goals. The challenge of addressing these delays requires a more efficient recruitment process to ensure timely hiring and avoid a negative impact on the company's operations. (Lufkin, 2021). All companies want to make sure that the kind of candidate they are picking for the role they are offering will be with them for a long. In this sense, job recruitment now really is about fit: firms want to make sure they are bringing the right person on board. The recruitment and selection process at Republic Gas Corporation is hindered by several challenges, including delays in document submission, difficulty in finding competent applicants, mismatches between applicants and job roles, fieldwork-related concerns, and overall delays in the hiring process. These issues not only extend the time required to hire the right candidates but also impact the company's operational efficiency and productivity. Addressing these challenges effectively is crucial for improving the recruitment process and ensuring that the company can hire qualified candidates promptly, thereby supporting its growth and success.

Challenges	Recommended Actions	Specific Activities	Proposed Solutions	Persons Involved	Success Indicators
1. Delays in Document Submission	Streamline the Documentation Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set clear deadlines for document submission during the recruitment process. - Communicate the importance of timely submission to applicants. - Create a standardized checklist of required documents. - Implement an automated system for document tracking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use software that tracks the submission process, sending notifications to both applicants and HR team when documents are missing or late. 	HR Department, Recruitment Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction in document submission delays. - Timely submission of all required documents.
2. Difficulty in Obtaining Certificates of Employment (COE)	Improve Communication with Previous Employers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assign dedicated personnel to follow up with applicants and previous employers regarding COE submission. - Set a specific timeframe for COE retrieval. - Collaborate with local employers for faster COE issuance. - Offer applicants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement partnerships with previous employers for fast-tracked COE requests or allow applicants to submit alternative documents proving employment. 	HR Department, Recruitment Coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Faster retrieval of COE or alternative documents. - Reduced delays in the hiring process.

		alternative documents (e.g., employment contracts).			
3. Lack of Competent or Qualified Applicants	Enhance Job Descriptions and Recruitment Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revise job descriptions to better align with the skills and experience needed. - Expand recruitment channels to target a broader pool of candidates. - Use multiple recruitment platforms (e.g., LinkedIn, job fairs, recruitment agencies). - Implement pre-screening tests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase job visibility on LinkedIn, attend job fairs, and partner with recruitment agencies for more outreach. 	Recruitment Team, Hiring Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased pool of qualified candidates. - Improved match between candidates' qualifications and job requirements.
4. Mismatch Between Applicants and Job Roles	Better Alignment of Applicants with Job Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review and update recruitment strategies to align job roles with applicants' qualifications and career goals. - Offer career counseling for applicants. - Provide detailed job previews during interviews. - Conduct competency-based interviews to better match skills to roles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide more in-depth interviews and job previews to ensure better alignment between applicants and job roles. 	HR Department, Hiring Managers, Career Counselors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased satisfaction from both applicants and hiring managers. - Better role fit.
5. Challenges with Fieldwork Roles	Highlight the Benefits and Support for Fieldwork Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct informational sessions to clarify the expectations of fieldwork positions. - Offer incentives for applicants to consider field-based roles. - Promote the benefits of field roles (e.g., career growth, bonuses). - Provide support structures (e.g., transport, safety). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer transportation, safety equipment, and career development incentives to attract applicants to field roles. 	HR Department, Field Managers, Marketing Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased number of applicants for fieldwork roles. - Positive feedback from fieldwork recruits.
6. Delays in the Hiring Process	Speed Up the Recruitment Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set clear timelines for each stage of the hiring process. - Improve internal communication to ensure timely processing. - Implement a more efficient applicant tracking system (ATS). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use an automated ATS to streamline the hiring process and ensure timely updates. 	HR Department, Recruitment Team, IT Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Faster hiring process from application to decision. - Increased hiring rate within a shorter time frame.

		- Establish a hiring team for quick decision-making.			
7. Difficulty in Attracting Female Applicants	Promote Gender Inclusivity and Equal Opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourage diversity in job advertisements and recruitment campaigns. - Address gender-specific concerns, especially regarding fieldwork roles. - Ensure gender-neutral job descriptions. - Promote a culture of inclusivity through employee resource groups. 	- Tailor job ads to appeal to a diverse group of applicants and create a more inclusive environment in the workplace.	HR Department, Marketing Team, Diversity & Inclusion Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in the number of female applicants. - Higher engagement in gender-inclusive campaigns.
8. Unqualified Applicants Applying for Positions	Improve Pre-Screening and Qualification Checks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce more rigorous pre-screening questions or tests to evaluate applicants' qualifications before interviews. - Implement competency-based assessments. - Filter applications more effectively to ensure only qualified candidates are considered. 	- Integrate AI or automated systems that can filter out unqualified applicants early in the process.	HR Department, Recruitment Team, Hiring Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease in unqualified applicants moving forward. - Higher quality of candidates reaching the interview stage.

CONCLUSION

The recruitment process of a Regasco uses a strategic approach to select and employ individuals who meet the company's technical and cultural requirements. To hire, their hiring criteria consider educational qualifications and work experience—skills required for the position. By assessing candidates across these criteria, Regasco is confident in hiring individuals who possess the necessary qualities and abilities to contribute positively to the company's long-term goals.

Hiring individuals into positions they are well-suited for holds great value for both the organization and the workers. It causes good performance, increased retention rates, and a steady, productive labor force, which are important in promoting long-term organizational success.

In conclusion, these challenges have a huge influence on the hiring process, which causes delays in filling positions and reduces operational effectiveness. Reduced worker capacity, slower production, and trouble reaching operational goals are all possible outcomes of these delays.

RECOMMENDATION

Regasco must improve its recruitment and hiring criteria to identify suitable candidates for vacant positions. By establishing clear, objective, and thorough criteria, they can better assess candidates' skills, experience, and cultural fit. A well-defined recruitment strategy not only helps in selecting the right talent but also contributes to the company's long-term success by building a strong, capable workforce. Continuous improvement of these criteria will lead to more informed hiring decisions and better organizational performance.

Set clear and effective hiring standards, simplify recruitment procedures, invest in ongoing employee development, and ensure a strong match between job roles and individual skills to improve performance and retention.

The researchers suggested that Regasco should enhance its recruiting and recruitment procedures for them to successfully identify and choose the top applicants. This involves simplifying the application process by minimizing the number of documents to be submitted and to provide clear and concise instructions to candidates. Additionally, it is recommended to refine the hiring process like developing a structured interview in order to making a fair interview with all of the applicants. Regasco may accomplish its strategic goals and develop a high-performing workforce by putting these changes into practice.

REFERENCES

- Aseen, A. (2015). Recruitment and selection process of higher education sector and its impact on organizational outcomes. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies* 5(4). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289494346_Recruitment_and_selection_process_of_higher_education_sector_and_its_impact_on_organizational_outcomes. Retrieved Date: May 23, 2024
- Asonitou, S., Vitouladiti, O. (2015). AN ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT GREEK TRAVEL AGENCIES POLICY ON RECRUITMENT, DUTIES, ONGOING TRAINING AND EMPLOYEE ADVANCEMENT. <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/pdf/10.5555/20173314617>. Retrieved Date: May 23, 2024
- Azami, M. (2021). What is Industry. https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/what-industry-milad-azami?trk=portfolio_article-card_title. Retrieved Date: July 11, 2024
- Bakti, S., Hwihanus, H. (2023). Analysis of the Effect of Recruitment, Management Efforts, Selection Criteria and Service Quality on Organizational Productivity with Employee Improvement as a Moderation Variable. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372671569_Analysis_of_the_Effect_of_Recruitment_Management_Efforts_Selection_Criteria_and_Service_Quality_on_Organizational_Productivity_with_Employee_Improvement_as_a_Moderation_Variable. Retrieved Date: May 21, 2024
- Bambekov, G. (2023). What Can Oil and Gas Companies Do to Attract Workers?. <https://www.oilandgasiq.com/operational-excellence/articles/where-have-all-the-workers-gone>. Retrieved Date: August 12, 2024
- Berzman, R. (2024). Q&A: How Long Does the Hiring Process Take? (With Steps). <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/starting-new-job/how-long-does-hiring-process-take>. Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024

- Boulet, G. (2021). The Difference Between Knowledge And Skills: Knowing Does Not Make You Skilled. <https://elearningindustry.com/difference-between-knowledge-and-skills-knowing-not-make-skilled>. Retrieved Date: July 6, 2024
- Cunningham, K. (2024). Engage and Retain 10 effective employee retention strategies. <https://www.skillssoft.com/blog/engage-and-retain-10-effective-employee-retention-strategies>. Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024
- Daniels, A. (2021). Understanding Recruitment and Selection in Human Resource Management. <https://www.businessstudynotes.com/hrm/human-resource-management/recruitment-and-selea>. Retrieved Date: June 26, 2024
- Duggan, J., Sherman, U., Carbery, R., & McDonnell, A. (2019). Algorithmic management and app-work in the gig economy: A research agenda for employment relations and HRM. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 30(1), 114–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12258>. Retrieved Date: May 25, 2024
- Eaton, B. (2024). 4 Examples of Gender Discrimination in Hiring Practices — And How To Address Them. <https://vervoe.com/gender-discrimination-in-hiring-practices/>. Retrieved Date: December 8, 2024
- Edwards, K. (2023). What Is Human Resource Management (HRM)?. <https://mosey.com/blog/what-is-human-resources-management/#:~:text=Kaitlin%20Edwards%20%7C%20Dec%2016%2C%202023,ensure%20a%20secure%20workplace%20environment>. Retrieved Date: May 23, 2024
- Eisner, C. (2022). Process vs Procedure: Key Differences Explained [+Examples]. <https://www.getmaintainx.com/blog/process-vs-procedure>. Retrieved Date: May 23, 2024
- Ekwoaba, J. O., Ikeije, U. U., Ufoma, N. (2015). THE IMPACT OF RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION CRITERIA ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management* 3 (2), 22-33. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362595517_THE_IMPACT_OF_RECRUITMENT_AND_SELECTION_CRITERIA_ON_ORGANIZATIONAL_PERFORMANCE/link/62f3a20852130a3cd70ff65a/download. Retrieved Date: May 28, 2024
- Garcia Jr., T. (2022). LPG blast damages Pagadian City commercial center. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1187835>. Retrieved Date: July 12, 2024
- Hammeed, G. A., Orifah, M. O., Ijeoma, M. C., Tijani, S. A. (2016). Assessment of the Use of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) as Cooking Energy Source Among Rural Households in Badagry Area of Lagos State. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/301520974_Assessment_of_the_Use_of_Liquefied_Petroleum_Gas_LPG_as_Cooking_Energy_Source_Among_Rural_Households_in_Badagry_Area_of_Lagos_State. Retrieved Date: July 4, 2024
- Hamza, P. A., Othman, B. J., Gardi, B., Sorguli, S., Aziz, H. M., Ahmed, S. A., Sabir, B. Y., Ismael, N. B., Ali, B., Anwar, K. (2021). Recruitment and Selection: The Relationship between Recruitment and Selection with Organizational Performance. *International Journal of Engineering Business and Management* 5(3). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351779948>. Retrieved Date: June 7, 2024
- Hasan, T., Kausik, A. (2024). Field Workers: Definition, Key Skills, Challenges, Considerations, and Trends. <https://www.fieldservicely.com/field-workers>. Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024

- Herrity, J. (2024). Work Experience and Your Career: Importance, Levels and Tips. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/finding-a-job/work-experience>. Retrieved Date: December 5, 2024
- Hiddemen, T., Howell, E., Blackford, T., Warren, L. (2018). Integrated planning for a dynamic oil and gas industry. <https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/pe/pdf/Publicaciones/TL/integrated-planning-for-oil-and-gas-Final-web.pdf>. Retrieved Date: May 28, 2024
- Hudik, R. (2019). Workforce Challenges Face the Oil and Natural Gas Industry. https://shalemag.com/workforce-challenges-face-the-oil-and-natural-gas-industry/?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTEAAR3rB4Xim0IumLmFPCEdVYLcvIw8OFDFKs4wcvNuyVz2x5ad-CfvWzVQ7QE_aem_72xfDcKVNCKKB4R2cyDF6g. Retrieved Date: July 12, 2024
- Jannen, B. J. (2018). What Does Qualifications Mean on a Job Application?. <https://work.chron.com/qualifications-mean-job-application-2113.html>. Retrieved Date: May 23, 2024
- Jorvogan, J. (2024). Top 11 Oil & Gas Recruiters, Headhunters, and Executive Search Firms. <https://jakejorgovan.com/blog/oil-gas-recruiters-headhunters-executive-search-firms>. Retrieved Date: March 19, 2024
- Kanason, E. (2018). 4 Key HR Challenges in the Oil and Gas Industry. <https://www.scrip.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=135778>. Retrieved Date: August 12, 2024
- Kapur, R. (2018). Recruitment and Selection. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323829919_Recruitment_and_Selection/citations. Retrieved Date: May 19, 2024
- Kapur, R. (2020). Importance of Recruitment and Selection in Leading to Progression of the Organization. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339123280_Importance_of_Recruitment_and_Selection_in_Leading_to_Progression_of_the_Organization. Retrieved Date: May 19, 2024
- Kaushik, A. (2024). 15 Effective Mass Hiring Strategies. <https://www.wecreateproblems.com/blog/mass-hiring-strategies>. Retrieved Date: May 19, 2024
- Kaushik, A. (2024). What is Candidate Selection? Importance, Criteria & Process. <https://www.wecreateproblems.com/blog/candidate-selection>. Retrieved Date: May 19, 2024
- Khalid, A. (2023). The Effect of Electronic Human Resource Management Systems on Sustainable Competitive Advantages: The Roles of Sustainable Innovation and Organizational Agility. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/23/16382>. Retrieved Date: May 28, 2024
- Lawrence, O. (2023). Top Five Challenges Facing the Oil and Gas industry. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/top-five-challenges-facing-oil-gas-industry-ogbonnah-mba-cpa-aca#:~:text=Published%20Mar%2011%2C%202023,electric%20vehicles%2C%20and%20automated%20p rocesses>. Retrieved Date: December 8, 2024
- Lhommeau, B., Remy, V. (2022). Candidate Selection Criteria: A Summary of the Recruitment Process. https://www.insee.fr/en/statistiques/fichier/6530566/04_ES534-35_Lhommeau-Remy_EN.pdf. Retrieved Date: March 17, 2024
- Lievens, F., & Chapman, D. S. (2017). Ensuring long-term fit: The role of recruitment and selection in organizational success. *Journal of Applied Psychology*.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281145504_Employment_Qualifications_Person-Job_Fit_Underemployment_Attributions_and_Hiring_Recommendations_A_three-study_investigation.

Retrieved Date: November 15, 2024

Lufkin, B. (2021). Why hiring takes so long. <https://www.bbc.com/worklife/article/20211020-why-hiring-takes-so-long>.

Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024

Mayhew, R. (2024). Appropriate Criteria for an Effective Recruitment & Selection Program. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/appropriate-criteria-effective-recruitment-selection-program-11101.html>.

Retrieved Date: May 23, 2024

McConnell, B. (2024). Candidate evaluation: tips and techniques to ensure the best hire. <https://recruitee.com/articles/candidate-evaluations#:~:text=Experience%20is%20critical%20in%20determining,reduce%20the%20loss%20of%20productivity>.

Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024

Merrell, J. M. (2024). Finding the Perfect M Person-Job Fit Drives Organizational Growth. https://workology.com/person_job_fit/. Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024

Meyer, C. (2024). Candidate Selection - Criteria, Process, and Examples. <https://www.thomas.co/resources/type/hr-blog/candidate-selection-criteria-process-and-examples>. Retrieved Date: February 27, 2024

Oleg, M. (2024). How to Streamline Your Hiring Process. <https://www.nimble.com/blog/how-to-streamline-your-hiring-process/>. Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024

Muspratt, A. (2019). The Top 10 Oil & Gas Companies in the World: 2019. <https://www.oilandgasiq.com/strategy-management-and-information/articles/oil-and-gas-companies>. Retrieved Date: July 4, 2024

Nallalingham, L. (2023). The Power of Objective Criteria. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/science-based-hiring-power-objective-criteria-lee-nallalingham>. Retrieved Date: March 17, 2024

Nguyen, T. (2022). Labor shortage remains a major challenge for oil and gas: Spring 2022 outlook. <https://realeconomy.rsmus.com/labor-shortage-remains-a-major-challenge-for-oil-and-gas-spring-2022-outlook/>. Retrieved Date: July 4, 2024

Rado. (2024). Criteria. <https://ayanza.com/dictionary/criteria>. Retrieved Date: March 17, 2024

Ramos, A. (2024). What is Skills-Based Hiring (And How to Implement It in Your Recruitment Process). <https://manilarecruitment.com/manila-recruitment-articles-advice/what-is-skills-based-hiring/>. Retrieved Date: December 6, 2024

Rao, P. (2024). Organizational Success: Strategies for Achieving and Sustaining Excellence. *Business Studies Journal*, 16(2), 1-2. <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/organizational-success-strategies-for-achieving-and-sustaining-excellence-17341.html#:~:text=Organizational%20success%20encompasses%20achieving%20long-term%20goals%2C%20maintaining%20high,strong%20leadership%2C%20employee%20engagement%2C%20customer%20focus%2C%20and%20innovation>. Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024.

- Rindé, S. (2024). Top 10 Most Common Recruiting Challenges in 2024 & How to Overcome Them. <https://fabricstaffing.com/top-10-most-common-recruiting-challenges-in-2024-how-to-overcome-them/?amp=1>. Retrieved Date: December 8, 2024
- Saleem, S., Tsui, Eric., Kuen See-To, E. W., Barendrecht, A.(2017). Knowledge retention and aging workforce in the oil and gas industry: a multi perspective study. *Journal of Knowledge Management*. 21. 00-00. 10.1108/JKM-07-2016-0281. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317418423_Knowledge_retention_and_aging_workforce_in_the_oil_and_gas_industry_a_multi_perspective_study. Retrieved Date: May 19, 2024
- Sawaneh, I. A., Kamara, F. K. (2019). Evaluating Employee Retention Strategies on Job Performance. <https://www.academia.edu/download/76489337/10.11648.j.sjbm.20190703.12.pdf>. Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024
- Schwencke, B.(2024). Candidate Selection: A Definitive Guide. <https://www.testpartnership.com/blog/candidate-selection.html>. Retrieved Date: December 6, 2024
- Sefcik, J. T. (2024). HOW JOB FIT ENHANCES EMPLOYEE RETENTION AND ORGANIZATIONAL SUCCESS. <https://employmenttechnologies.com/job-fit-the-key-to-employee-retention-and-success/>. Retrieved Date: December 28, 2024
- Soper, J. (2024). What to Look for in an Employee: Top 12 Qualities of a New Hire. <https://fitsmallbusiness.com/what-to-look-for-in-an-employee/>. Retrieved Date: May 29, 2024
- Spacey, J. (2023). 103 Examples of Selection Criteria. <https://simplicable.com/en/selection-criteria>. Retrieved Date: May 25, 2024
- Strikwerda, L. (2022). How to Hire Employees: Define Your Hiring Selection Criteria. <https://www.applicantstack.com/blog/how-to-do-prescreening-preparation/>. Retrieved Date: May 30, 2024
- Sujan, C. (2023). What is an Organization? Definition, Features, Examples, Process, and Importance. <https://thembains.com/organization/>. Retrieved Date: May 23, 2024
- Tanu., Vaishnavi., Ananya. (2023). An Analytical Study on Recruitment and Selection Process in Sinzo Pvt. Ltd. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 4, no 7, pp 476-480. <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V4ISSUE7/IJRPR15269.pdf>. Retrieved Date: March 25, 2024
- Teeuwen, W. (2022). Challenges of competency-based hiring. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/challenges-competency-based-hiring-wiebe-teeuwen>. Retrieved Date: December 8, 2024
- Try, K. (2018). What are the risks of a delayed recruitment process?. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/what-risks-delayed-recruitment-process-kimlay-try/>. Retrieved Date: December 8, 2024
- Trysantika, S., Frianto, A., Kristyanto, A., Fazlurrahman, H. (2023). The Effect of Person-Job Fit on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. *Social Science Studies* 3(6):470-484. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376381727_The_Effect_of_Person-Job_Fit_on_Employee_Performance_Through_Job_Satisfaction_as_an_Intervening_Variable?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTEAAR0JsQt5hFVbnhFltc-y9228IUkiYnZcTJDzGGzlcA_NHDz_X3YKEU5D64_aem_XJ9Ji8TT3Fv-HSFtMe002w. Retrieved Date: December 21, 2024

- Tucker, K. (2023). The Surprising Impact of a Long Hiring Process on Recruitment Success and Budgets. <https://www.lanteria.com/news/surprising-impact-long-hiring-process-recruitment-success-and-budgets>. Retrieved Date: December 8, 2024
- Urin, M. (2024). How to Write Job Requirements. <https://builtin.com/recruiting/job-requirements>. Retrieved Date: May 29, 2024
- Varga, R. J. (2024). The Mismatch - not all hires are meant to be. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/mismatch-all-hires-meant-rita-j-varga-cipd-she-sie-ella--31d7f>. Retrieved Date: December 25, 2024
- Zhang, S., Huang, W., Li, H. (2023). Effects of person-job fit on occupational commitment among kindergarten teachers: occupational well-being as mediator and perceived organizational support as moderator. https://bmcpyschology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40359-023-01441-7?utm_source. Retrieved Date: May 23, 2024
- Zivkovic, M. (2024). The 13 Biggest Recruiting Challenges & How to Overcome Them. <https://toggl.com/blog/recruiting-challenges>. Retrieved Date: December 8, 2024
- Ziwewe, N. (2024). Why Is Work Experience Important To Get Employed?. <https://www.thehumancapitalhub.com/articles/Why-Is-Work-Experience-Important-To-Get-Employed>. Retrieved Date: December 5, 2024